

Supplementary data

Table S1. Expression of genes coding for enzymes modifying cell-wall polysaccharides in BS1 ovules compared to expression in revertant ovules. RNA was extracted from ovules, and libraries were prepared. All genes of cell-wall-modifying enzymes (n=3) in BS1 ovules exhibited significant expression ($p < 0.05$) compared to revertant ovules and are expressed as log₂ fold change.

Enzyme	Gene name/ transcript ID	Log2 fold change	Differentially expressed genes in BS1
Xyloglucan xyloglucosyl transferase [EC:2.4.1.207]	<i>Ofi_XT1</i>	+2.24	Up regulation
	<i>Ofi_XT2</i>	+2.04	
	<i>Ofi_XT3</i>	+1.79	
	<i>Ofi_XT4</i>	+1.28	
	<i>Ofi_XT5</i>	+5.70	
	<i>Ofi_XT6</i>	+0.98	
	<i>Ofi_XT7</i>	+1.51	
	<i>Ofi_XT8</i>	+2.26	
	<i>Ofi_XT9</i>	+1.78	
	<i>Ofi_XT10</i>	+2.51	
	<i>Ofi_XT11</i>	+2.89	
	<i>Ofi_XT12</i>	+1.78	
Pectinesterase [EC:3.1.1.11]	<i>Ofi_PE1</i>	+1.05	Up regulation
	<i>Ofi_PE2</i>	+0.89	
	<i>Ofi_PE3</i>	+1.91	
	<i>Ofi_PE4</i>	+0.67	
Cellulose synthase-like protein [EC:2.4.1.-]	<i>Ofi_CSLD1</i>	+1.89	Up regulation
Polygalacturonase [EC:3.2.1.15]	<i>Ofi_PG1</i>	+10.99	Up regulation
Xyloglucan 6-xylosyltransferase [EC:2.4.2.39]	<i>Ofi_XXT1</i>	+1.28	Up regulation

Enzyme	Gene name/ transcript ID	Log2 fold change	Differentially expressed genes in BS1
Chitinase [EC:3.2.1.14]	<i>Ofi_CHIT1</i>	+3.02	Up regulation
	<i>Ofi_CHIT2</i>	+1.62	
	<i>Ofi_CHIT3</i>	+3.27	
	<i>Ofi_CHIT4</i>	+1.37	
Endoglucanase [EC:3.2.1.4]	<i>Ofi_EG1</i>	-2.11	Down regulation
	<i>Ofi_EG2</i>	-1.54	
	<i>Ofi_EG3</i>	-1.58	
	<i>Ofi_EG4</i>	-1.49	
Galacturan 1,4-alpha-galacturonidase [EC:3.2.1.67]	<i>Ofi_GAG1</i>	-6.02	Up/down regulation
	<i>Ofi_GAG2</i>	+0.80	
β-galactosidase [EC:3.2.1.23]	<i>Ofi_BGA1</i>	+0.63	Up regulation
	<i>Ofi_BGA2</i>	+2.11	
	<i>Ofi_BGA3</i>	+1.02	
	<i>Ofi_BGA4</i>	+0.79	
Beta-glucosidase [EC:3.2.1.21]	<i>Ofi_BGL1</i>	+1.07	Up regulation
	<i>Ofi_BGL2</i>	+2.93	
	<i>Ofi_BGL3</i>	+2.86	
	<i>Ofi_BGL4</i>	+1.10	
	<i>Ofi_BGL5</i>	+1.78	
	<i>Ofi_BGL6</i>	+0.94	
	<i>Ofi_BGL7</i>	+0.85	
	<i>Ofi_BGL8</i>	+3.99	

Fig. S1. Transcriptome analysis of BS1 and revertant (Rev). (A) Differential expression of genes in BS1 and Rev. (B) Scatter plot of transformed expression in BS1 and Rev, showing a strong positive relationship. (C) Box plot showing a comparative analysis of data dispersion within and between the BS1 and revertant groups for transformed data distribution. (D) Phylogenetic tree showing the genetic relationships between BS1 and Rev groups. (E) PCA analysis of BS1 versus revertant. (F) Hierarchical clustering. (G) Volcano plot of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (Inset: MA plot of DEGs).